

Researcher Experience Panel

Chaired by Prof Richard de Grijs (@tallstarman), Macquarie University, Sydney 0000-0002-7203-5996

- Prof Diana Kornbrot (@dekaliss) 0000-0002-7166-589X
 - University of Hertfordshire
- Prof Simon Tanner (@SimonTanner) 0000-0001-6740-7962
 - King's College London
- Prof Brad Gibson (@profbradgibson) 0000-0003-4446-3130
 - University of Hull
- Prof Roderic Page (@rdmpage) 0000-0002-7101-9767
 - University of Glasgow

- » Richard de Grijs is an acclaimed astrophysicist and prolific public speaker. Born and raised in the Netherlands, his successful career has allowed him to enjoy vibrant research environments in the USA (University of Virginia), the UK (Universities of Cambridge and Sheffield) and China (Peking University). In March 2018, Richard moved to Macquarie University in Sydney, Australia, as Associate Dean (Global Engagement). He received a number of prestigious awards, including the 2012 Selby Award for excellence in science from the Australian Academy of Science, a Visiting Academy Professorship from the Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences, and a 2017 Erskine Award for interdisciplinary science and student mentoring from the University of Canterbury (New Zealand). He served as researcher member on the ORCID Board of Directors from 2017 to 2019.
- » Diana Kornbrot is Professor Emeritus of Mathematical Psychology at the University of Hertfordshire. Her research covers areas from Mathematical Models of the Psychology of Thinking through Higher Education and Technology to Evolutionary Psychology. She is a passionate advocate of Open Science.
- » Simon Tanner is [Professor of Digital Cultural Heritage](#) in the [Department of Digital Humanities](#) at King's College London. He is a digital humanities scholar with a wide-ranging interest in cross-disciplinary thinking and collaborative approaches that reflect a fascination with interactions between memory institution collections (libraries, museum, archives, media and publishing) and the digital domain.
- » Professor Brad Gibson is Head of Physics & Maths and Director of the E.A. Milne Centre for Astrophysics at the University of Hull. Brad's research spans the determination of the expansion rate of the Universe, the origin of the chemical elements, and the construction of the world's first liquid mirror telescope. He is Scientific Editor for The Astrophysical Journal, and delivers ~100 engagement and public outreach events per year, reaching in excess of one million people in the past three years.
- » Rod Page is Professor of Taxonomy at the University of Glasgow. He says he is a lapsed taxonomist who worked on phylogenetic methods before deciding to tackle the challenge of integrating biodiversity data into a "knowledge graph". As such he spends little time in his own ORCID profile but instead spends time grappling with the API, interfacing with wikidata – all this driven by a desire to link people, publications, and the scientific names of plants and animals.